

"IMAGE AND SPECTROSCOPY: A NOVEL NON-DESTRUCTIVE TECHNOLOGIES FOR QUALITY ASSESSMENT OF FRUITS & VEGETABLES: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW"

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Abstract

The review paper explores the advancements in non-destructive technologies for the quality assessment of fruits and vegetables, focusing on non-invasive methods like image processing and spectroscopy. The need for accurate and efficient quality inspection is emphasized, given the impact of external and internal quality attributes on consumer behavior and economic outcomes. The paper discusses various techniques, including image processing for external inspection and spectroscopic methods like UV-Vis and near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy, for analyzing internal quality. These methods provide valuable insights into the structural and compositional properties of agricultural products without compromising their integrity, making them superior to traditional destructive methods. The review highlights the challenges in automating quality inspection processes and the potential of these technologies to improve accuracy and efficiency in quality control.

Keywords: non-destructive detection; non-invasive technology; Image Processing; post-harvest technology; Fruit Quality, fruits; vegetables.

Introduction:

The advancement of science and technology, particularly information technology, has provided numerous non-destructive methods for analysing materials, which can also be utilized for fruits and vegetables. Generally, quality refers to meeting consumers' expectations regarding the safety, storability, and sensory characteristics of products. Sensory characteristics include appearance (color, shape, and defects), texture (crispness, juiciness, firmness, toughness, etc.), and flavour (taste and aroma). (P. Eccher Zerbini 2005).

Methods to measure fruit quality can be destructive or non-destructive. Unlike traditional testing methods that could potentially cause damage, Non-destructive technologies can perform thorough evaluation without compromising the structural integrity of the materials being tested.

Both external and internal quality of fresh fruits and vegetables are important sensory attribute. The outer appearance of fruits and vegetables affects consumer's buying behaviour, and sometimes the defective, infected and contaminated fruits and vegetables can spread the infection or contamination to the sound products even the whole batch, thus causing great economic losses. (ElMasry *et al.*, 2008; Gomez-Sanchis *et al.*, 2008; Li *et al.*, 2011; Xing *et al.*, 2005).

Automatic quality inspection of fruits and vegetables is still a challenging work. Some external quality criteria, such as color, texture, size, and shape, are automated on industrial graders, but grading of fruits and vegetables based on appearance criteria such as bruises, rottenness, and other subtle defects that have the same color and texture as the healthy peel, or defects that are easily mistaken for the stem-end and calyxes, is not yet efficient. As a result, this process still relies on manual operation. (Leemans & Destain, 2004). Manual operation has some drawbacks such as inconsistency, time consuming, variability and subjectivity, besides, the manual process is also very tedious, laborious, costly, and easily influenced by the surrounding environment (ElMasry *et al.*, 2012). So, it is important and necessary

to develop a non-destructive quality inspection system to replace manual inspection.

2. Non-Destructive Methods

Non-destructive evaluation (NDE) involves examining an object using technology that does not compromise its future usability, according to the American Society of Non-destructive Testing (ASNT, 2012). The core principle of NDE is to assess the quality or integrity of an item without causing damage, identifying a physical phenomenon (the interrogating parameter) that interacts with and is influenced by the test specimen (the interrogated parameter) without affecting its function (Shull, 2002).

Non-destructive methods are effective because they are based on physical properties that correlate with certain quality factors of fruits and vegetables. In addition, they do not rupture the fruit tissue and can be used to assess the internal structure and quality of fruits and vegetables. (A. Adedeji *et al.* 2020) This review presents a general overview of current non-destructive techniques for the detection of internal and external quality of fresh fruits and vegetables and discusses basic principles of image processing, spectroscopy technique, and their applications.

Image Processing

Image processing works with images to enhance their features and make them easier to analyse. There are three levels of image processing and analysis:

Low-level processing involves basic tasks like image acquisition and pre-processing. Image pre-processing can improve the quality of the acquired images by increasing the contrast, removing the blur and noise, and correcting the distortion.

Intermediate-level processing is a crucial step that includes tasks such as image segmentation, feature extraction, representation, and description.

High-level processing is the final step, which includes tasks like recognition, interpretation, and classification for image analysis. (B. Zhang *et al.*, 2014).

Fig.1 Different levels of image processing (Du & Sun, 2004).

K. Komal et al. (2019), studied the technique of SVM classifier to classify the defective and non-defective regions of an image. The SVM classifier detects the percentage of defective and non-defective areas of the orange fruit for quality assessment.

The proposed methodology:

Start: Initiate the process.

Input Image: Capture an image of the orange.

Pre-processing: Check for and remove any noise in the fruit image.

Apply region-based segmentation to select the Region of Interest.

Extract features using the GLCM algorithm.

Classification: Classify the image into defective and non-defective portions.

Define a hyperplane for the classification.

Apply SVM classifier for image classification.

9. Generate results showing fruit defectiveness.

10. Stop: End the process after obtaining results.

Spectroscopy is the study of the way light (electromagnetic radiation) and matter interact. There are several different types of spectroscopic techniques and the basic principle shared by all is to shine a beam of a particular electromagnetic radiation onto a sample and observe how it responds to such a stimulus; allowing scientists to obtain information about the structure and properties of matter. (www.rsc.org).

Spectroscopic techniques are diverse and include methods like ultraviolet-visible (UV-Vis) spectroscopy, near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy, and so on. Each technique has its unique applications and advantages, making spectroscopy a versatile tool in scientific research.

Fig.3 From Wikimedia Commons

UV-Vis (Ultraviolet-Visible) Spectroscopy

UV and visible use wavelengths (180-900 nm) & are frequently used in the same instrument. In this range, absorption spectra are produced from the transition of electrons from their lowest energy state to higher energy states. The maximum absorption in this spectral range for specific compounds corresponds to the material's structure, geometry, and symmetry. This principle is most commonly observed in the formation of coloured compounds in many analytical methods. These coloured compounds can be detected by spectroscopy in the visible region, and the intensity of the color is directly related to the concentration of the substance being studied. In food analysis, color measurement is perhaps the most significant application of the visible region. At specific wavelengths, the UV region can also be used to

measure fluorescence (the ability of some atomic structures to emit, rather than absorb. (Christopher N.G. Scatter)

Near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy

Near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy is based on the absorption of electromagnetic radiation at wavelengths in the range of 780–2500 nm (fig 1). NIR spectra of foods comprise broad bands arising from overlapping absorptions corresponding mainly to overtones and combinations of vibrational modes involving C-H, O-H, and N-H chemical bonds. NIR, like all radiation, behaves as a wave with the properties of simple harmonic motion which may be defined in terms of two properties:

> The frequency of vibration

$$= \text{no. of times the wave pattern is repeated in 1 se} \\ = \frac{\text{angular velocity}}{2}$$

> The wavelength

$$= \frac{\text{velocity of light}}{\text{frequency}}$$

Fig.4 Principal types of NIR absorption bands and their locations. (Brian G. Osborne 2006)

Fig.2 Different stages of the proposed segmentation process. (a)Input image (RGB) (b) Remove background. (c) Gray level image.(d) Original image.(e) Resulting diseases image. (K. Komal et al. 2019)

2. Spectroscopy Technique

Fig.5 An overview of principle, methods and applications of NIRS. (Soo-In Sohn et al ,2021)

Basic operational procedure

The typical procedures of NIRS are as follows. First, the chemical compositions in food are analysed using an external standard detection method. Second, NIRS is used to rapidly analyse the chemical profile variances in samples. Finally, a prediction model is built using the chemometrics method to predict and analyse unknown samples.

The analytical information contained in the typically broad bands of NIR spectra is hardly selective and is influenced by a number of physical, chemical, and structural variables. NIRS requires chemometrics to extract as much relevant information as possible from the analytical data. With the development of technology, chemometrics methods have been improved and developed to enhance their ability to analyse the chemical profile variances and predict the count of target composition, indicating that NIRS could be better used in the detection of food contaminants and food quality evaluation.

Chemometrics methods

Chemometrics is the science of extracting information from chemical systems via mathematical and statistical methods. NIRS requires chemometrics to extract as much relevant information as possible to construct classification and calibration models. With the invention of the computer and its subsequent development, chemometrics has developed into a research field in its own right, which promotes the development and application of NIRS significantly. According to their purpose and the algorithms or computational procedures, chemometrics methods could be classified into quantitative analysis and qualitative analysis. The best-known and most widely used method for the reduction of variables is a principal component analysis (PCA), which allows dimensions of the original data to be reduced to a few uncorrelated variables. (Cozzolino et al , 2003)

Soft independent modelling of class analogy (SIMCA) is the best-known and most widely used method in qualitative multivariate analysis, whose models the space occupied by a class and determines whether a sample belongs to it on the basis of distance measurements or residual variance. Quantitative analyses in NIRS usually rely on the use of constructed spectral libraries. (Sáiz-Abajo et al ,2003)

The simplest quantitative analysis method is multiple linear regression (MLR), which usually uses fewer than five spectral wavelengths. MLR assumes concentration is a function of absorbance, which entails knowledge of the concentrations of not only the target analyses, but also all other components contributing to the overall signal.

The most frequently used multivariate-regression methods in NIR spectroscopy are principal component regression, and partial least-squares (PLS) regression.

However, the spectral data and the target property are not linearly related as a result of instrumental factors or the physical-chemical characteristics of the sample. These cases could be addressed using nonlinear calibration methods, particularly prominent among which are artificial neural networks. Hence there is no best chemometrics model for all applications. An appropriate combination of these models is needed for relevant analysis in various applications.

H Chopra et al. (2021) stated that optical spectrophotometry has been widely used for modern applications in food quality analysis and post-harvest inspection of fruits and vegetables. Both UV-Vis spectroscopy and near-infrared spectroscopy methods have been used to identify the quality of various fruits. The Spectroscopy sensor was selected as SparkFun's Triad Spectroscopy Sensor (AS7265x). Apple was pre-labelled as category 1, 2, & 3 (A, B, C) based on uniformity in peel color. The color of A-grade apples varies between 70-100%, B-grade

50-70%, and C-grade 0-100% respectively. (Md. Shamsher Ahmad et al., 2014) Apples were graded using this sensor. The sensor was able to

capture 18 readings, of each apple, representing different wavelengths (410-940 nm).

Table.1 Three Distinct Spectroscopy Samples from the dataset.

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	Label
1538.58	486.8	947.2	340.16	945.05	1844.74	324.7	353.83	162.93	111.23	256.41	97.84	1845.95	447.2	362.75	202.52	350.88	757.35	1
464.7	167.11	333.92	110.32	270.46	474.42	114.22	189.81	131.48	110.31	265.8	81.04	1340	278.72	312.93	165.55	343.97	718.48	2
269.45	111.71	225.75	52.4	111.27	206.15	35.37	57.6	90.99	73.54	154.38	51.39	759.49	302.64	190.55	105.88	235.08	557.12	3

Fig.7 ANOVA Test for Feature Importance

Conclusion

The comprehensive review demonstrates that non-destructive technologies, such as image processing and spectroscopic techniques, are important in advancing the quality assessment of fruits and vegetables. These methods enable precise, efficient, and non-invasive analysis, which is crucial for meeting consumer expectations and reducing economic losses due to quality issues. Despite the challenges in automating certain aspects of quality inspection, the continued development and integration of these technologies hold promise for significantly improving the consistency and reliability of quality control in the agricultural sector. Future research and technological advancements are essential to overcome current limitations and fully realize the potential of non-destructive methods in enhancing food safety and quality.

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Fig.6 (Xichang Wang2019)

Classification of the major chemometrics methods used in NIRS. ANN, Artificial neural networks; PCA, principal component analysis; PLS, partial least squares; PCR, principal component regression; MLR, multiple linear regression; SIMCA, soft independent modeling of class analogy; KNN, K-nearest neighbor; LDA, linear discriminant analysis.